

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.03.2024.5
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12692145
UDC: 338.48:331.5/.6-053.6(075.8)
JEL: I10; Z32

THE ROLE OF TOURISM IN THE SOCIAL INTEGRATION OF PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

РОЛЬ ТУРИЗМУ ДЛЯ ЛЮДЕЙ З ОБМЕЖЕНИМИ МОЖЛИВОСТЯМИ У СОЦІАЛЬНІЙ ІНТЕГРАЦІЇ

Natalia A. Dobrianska, Doctor of Economics, Professor
Odesa National University of Technology, Odesa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0002-0826-8840
Email: n.a.dobrianska@gmail.com

Denys.S. Kurchenko
Odesa National University of Technology, Odesa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0009-0000-1411-1770
Email: dep.tour.ontu@gmail.com

Oleksandra O. Nesterchuk
Odesa National University of Technology, Odesa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0009-0005-7800-0101
Email: nesterchuk.aleksandra@ukr.net

Received 10.04.2024

Добрянська Н.А., Курченко Д.С., Нестерчук О.О. Роль туризму для людей з обмеженими можливостями у соціальній інтеграції. Оглядова стаття.

У статті розглянуто ключові аспекти, пов'язані з інклюзивним туризмом та його впливом на соціальну інтеграцію осіб з інвалідністю в Україні за період 2017-2021 років. Стаття висвітлює зростання кількості людей із інвалідністю та визначає концепцію інклюзивного туризму, його розвиток і мету сприяння включенню цільової аудиторії в суспільство. Досліджено взаємозв'язок інклюзивного туризму і соціальної інтеграції, висвітлено важливість участі осіб з обмеженими можливостями у туристичних подіях та програмах. Також аналізується вплив пандемії COVID-19 на інклюзивний туризм та з'ясовуються можливості подолання труднощів, що виникають у зв'язку із забороною подорожей. Отже, стаття висвітлює важливість інклюзивного туризму як інструменту соціальної інтеграції та розглядає актуальні питання, пов'язані з розвитком цього напрямку, враховуючи не лише попит на такі послуги, а й виклики, що виникають у зв'язку із зовнішніми обставинами, такими як пандемія.

Ключові слова: туризм, туризм для людей з обмеженими можливостями, інклюзивний туризм, інклюзивність, туризм для всіх

Dobrianska N.A., Kurchenko D.S., Nesterchuk O.O. The Role of Tourism for People with Disabilities in Social Integration. Review article.

The article explores key aspects related to inclusive tourism and its impact on the social integration of individuals with disabilities in Ukraine during the period from 2017 to 2021. It highlights the increase in the number of people with disabilities and defines the concept of inclusive tourism, its development, and its purpose to facilitate the inclusion of the target audience into society. The interconnection between inclusive tourism and social integration is investigated, emphasizing the importance of the participation of individuals with disabilities in tourist events and programs. The article also analyzes the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on inclusive tourism and explores possibilities for overcoming difficulties arising from travel restrictions. In conclusion, the article emphasizes the significance of inclusive tourism as a tool for social integration and addresses pertinent issues related to the development of this field, considering not only the demand for such services but also the challenges arising from external factors, such as the pandemic.

Keywords: tourism, tourism for people with disabilities, inclusive tourism, inclusiveness, tourism for everyone

The relevance of the topic regarding the role of tourism for people with disabilities in social integration is based on several factors. These include social isolation and stereotypes, improvement of life quality, an inclusive society, broadening of cultural understanding, and the necessity of infrastructure adaptation.

Concerning social isolation, individuals with disabilities often encounter it along with stereotypes. Therefore, tourism can serve as an effective tool in reducing barriers, fostering social cohesion, and promoting positive perceptions. Participation in tourist events and programs can lead to improvements in physical and emotional health, as well as broaden opportunities for entertainment and life satisfaction. Promoting accessibility and inclusivity in tourism contributes to building a society that considers the needs of all its members. This is crucial for fostering an inclusive approach across various aspects of life. Additionally, the development of tourism for people with disabilities brings economic benefits, including the creation of new jobs and the development of specialized tourist services. Moreover, tourism can enhance cultural understanding and promote greater interaction among diverse socio-cultural groups, which helps address issues and foster healthy mutual understanding. Studying and adapting tourist infrastructure to accommodate the needs of various consumer groups is an important task, significantly facilitating access to tourist resources for people with disabilities.

The relevance of this analyzed topic is defined by the need to address real problems of social isolation and stereotypes, improve life quality, and create a more

inclusive society, where every individual has equal opportunities to participate in social, cultural, and recreational activities.

In contemporary society, the theme of social justice and inclusivity is becoming increasingly important. Tourism can play a key role in ensuring equal opportunities for all, including people with disabilities, by enabling them to actively participate in social life and cultural exchange. Interest in the development of inclusive tourism is growing, with strategies and programs aimed at creating accessible environments for tourists with disabilities, such as adapted hotels, transportation, and excursions, helping to expand travel opportunities for this category of people. The travels of people with disabilities can help broaden society's perspective, increase tolerance levels, and improve relations between different socio-cultural groups. Overall, the topic of the role of tourism for people with disabilities in social integration remains relevant and requires further research and development, as it contributes to creating a more inclusive and equitable society.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Recent research and publications in the field of inclusive tourism are conducted by scholars and researchers from various disciplines, including tourism studies, sociology, psychology, rehabilitation sciences, and others. Among the researchers who study the issues of inclusive tourism are V.V. Borysenko and Ya.O. Barybina, K.O. Chupina, A.I. Voytovska, L.Yu. Matviychuk and L.M. Chepurda, O.M. Radionova and A.S. Bezpalova. Experts from different organizations also contribute significantly to the research on tourism for people with disabilities. Specifically, experts from the World Tourism Organization, the World Health Organization (WHO), the All-Ukrainian Center for Vocational Rehabilitation of Persons with Disabilities, the National Assembly of People with Disabilities of Ukraine, the Fund for Social Protection of Persons with Disabilities, and the Department for Disability Affairs of the Ministry of Labor and Social Policy of Ukraine study and analyze various aspects of the issue of inclusive tourism. Their research aims to identify effective strategies, improve accessibility, and create favorable conditions for the participation of individuals with disabilities in tourist events and activities.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The problem of social isolation and limited participation of people with disabilities in social and cultural life has become increasingly pertinent due to the challenges they face. Such isolation may arise from physical limitations as well as from stereotypes and

inadequate infrastructure adaptation. In this context, the role of tourism can be pivotal in facilitating social integration and providing access to various social events and recreational activities. It is necessary to scientifically study the effectiveness of tourism programs and initiatives in positively impacting the social integration of people with disabilities. It is important to identify and address the barriers hindering active participation of this group of people in tourist journeys. Additionally, there is a need to develop informational campaigns to foster a positive attitude towards tourism for people with disabilities and reduce stereotypes.

Despite significant progress in the development of inclusive tourism, there are still some unresolved issues related to the role of tourism for people with disabilities in social integration.

While some countries and cities have already taken measures to create accessible environments for tourists with disabilities, there still exists a lack of adapted hotels, transportation, and other tourist attractions. Many tourism operators and service providers lack sufficient education and awareness regarding the needs of people with disabilities, which can lead to unsuitability or inadequate service for this audience. For many people with disabilities, the costs of inclusive tourism services may be too high, limiting their ability to travel and participate in social life. Achieving social integration for people with disabilities in tourism requires joint efforts from governmental bodies, civil society organizations, tourism operators, and other stakeholders. Innovations in the development of new technologies and solutions can make tourism more accessible for people with disabilities, but there is a need to incentivize such initiatives and research.

Addressing these unresolved issues will require concerted efforts and engagement of all stakeholders to create a more inclusive tourism environment.

The aim of the article is to study and elucidate the key role of tourism in the social integration of individuals with disabilities. Through an analysis of the relationship between tourism and social integration, the article aims to identify the positive impact of tourist activities on improving the quality of life of the target audience. It seeks to investigate the difficulties and obstacles faced by people with disabilities in the field of tourism and underscore the importance of developing inclusive approaches in tourism to support the social integration of individuals with disabilities.

The main part

According to research conducted by the World Health Organization, there are approximately one billion people with disabilities worldwide [9].

Table 1. Number of people with disabilities in Ukraine for the period 2017-2021, in thousands of hryvnias

	Years				
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Total, thousand individuals	2603,0	2635,6	2659,7	2703,0	2724,1
Group I	240,6	235,4	226,3	222,3	215,0
Group II	900,5	899,2	896,1	900,8	897,1
Group III	1306,2	1341,9	1375,7	1416,0	1449,1
Children with disabilities	156,1	159,0	161,6	163,9	162,9

Source: compiled by authors on materials [10]

Based on the data presented in the table, there is a trend of an increase in the number of people with disabilities over the study period. Inclusive tourism serves as a process aimed at reducing the social isolation of people with disabilities by enhancing their participation in all spheres of modern society.

According to the information available on the official website of the Fund for Social Protection of Persons with Disabilities in Ukraine, "inclusive tourism for people with disabilities" is defined as a modern form of tourism that allows the inclusion of any person in tourist activities, regardless of their physical abilities, taking into account the peculiarities of their physical and psychological condition. This encompasses various aspects such as medical, psychological, psychopedagogical, professional, labor-related, physical, social, and others.

Inclusive tourism is a form of tourism created to ensure accessibility of travel and leisure for all individuals, regardless of their physical, social, or economic constraints. Social integration in the context of inclusive tourism means creating conditions under which all members of society can participate in tourism activities without restrictions or discrimination.

The development of inclusive tourism can have significant social and economic impact, contributing to the improvement of the quality of life of the inclusive audience and generally fostering the building of a more open and understanding society.

One of the key advantages of inclusive tourism is ensuring equal opportunities for all, regardless of their physical, social, or cognitive characteristics. The creation of accessible infrastructure and the development of specialized tourism programs contribute to the inclusion of all groups of people in tourism activities. This not only facilitates travel for the inclusive audience but also fosters society's positive attitude towards diversity and inclusion.

The social interaction between inclusive tourists and local communities can lead to the exchange of experiences, understanding, and respect. During such interactions, new social connections are formed, promoting mutual understanding and tolerance.

At the economic level, inclusive tourism opens up new opportunities for the development of the tourism industry. Specialized services and programs attract new tourists, which can lead to an increase in tourist flows and the creation of new jobs.

Overall, inclusive tourism contributes to the creation of a more inclusive and diverse society, where every individual has the opportunity not only to discover new places but also to actively interact with others and contribute to the community.

Key factors of the role of inclusive tourism in social integration include:

Accessibility: Inclusive tourism contributes to the creation of accessible environments and services for all tourists, including people with disabilities, enabling them to actively participate in tourist travels and engage in society.

Social inclusion: Inclusive tourism expands opportunities for social interaction, helps reduce social

isolation, and promotes understanding among different population groups.

Inclusive tourism can also serve as a source of economic development for communities that were previously excluded or had limited access to tourism resources. This can create new jobs and support the development of territories. Inclusive tourism contributes to raising awareness and understanding of the importance of diversity in society – it can serve as a tool to combat stereotypes and promote positive perceptions of different population groups. Regarding cultural exchange, inclusive tourism stimulates cultural exchange between different groups, promotes mutual understanding, and enhances the appreciation of various cultures, thereby fostering cultural integration.

In the modern world, tourism is recognized not only as a means of leisure and entertainment but also as a powerful tool for promoting social integration and improving the quality of life for all citizens. In particular, research on the role of tourism for people with disabilities becomes a relevant topic as they often face social challenges and stereotypes. This conclusion underscores the need to consider tourism as a significant factor in addressing issues of social isolation and promoting the creation of a more inclusive society.

Tourism and social integration are interconnected in various aspects. Intercultural interaction in tourism contributes to the understanding and exchange of cultural values. Economic development through tourism can improve the social conditions of a region. Cultural exchange and community building influence the formation of an open society. The development of infrastructure in tourism zones affects the quality of life. Tourism stimulates socio-cultural exchange and contributes to the formation of new social connections. All these factors interact, determining the impact of tourism on social integration, which can be complex and dependent on various conditions and circumstances.

People with disabilities and those with diverse access needs travel and are likely to travel together with others. According to the accessibility study by Amadeus, these tourists represent a "\$70 billion market" just in Europe and the United States alone [8].

"Tourism for All" is a concept aimed at the growing segment of travelers with diverse needs and requirements. What is considered "accessible" for one traveler with a disability (for example, a wheelchair user) may be too challenging or completely unsuitable for another traveler with a different type of disability, mobility impairment, or other conditions. Therefore, increasing inclusivity becomes a more justified goal for the tourism industry, as it encompasses a broader range of needs and opportunities compared to a limited focus solely on "accessible tourism."

In the context of inclusivity and the development of tourism for all, a key concept underlying decision-making by tourism enterprises and directions is universal design.

Universal design is the process of designing and creating an environment in such a way that it can be easily accessed, understood, and used by the widest

range of people, regardless of their age, size, abilities, or disabilities. The environment, building, product, or service should be designed to meet the needs of everyone who wishes to use them. It is not just a special requirement for minority populations but rather a fundamental condition for achieving a high level of

design. If the environment is accessible, convenient, and user-friendly, all stakeholders benefit from it.

Let's consider the principles that underlie the system of inclusive tourism in European, Asian, and American tourist regions in Table 2.

Table 2. System of Principles of Universal Design "Accessible and Convenient for All"

Principle 1: Equal Use	Principle of equality and accessibility of the environment for everyone - providing equal means for all users to avoid singling out specific population groups. Design should be useful and easy to perceive and use for people with different levels of abilities.
Principle 2: Flexibility in Use	Design should ensure the availability of a wide range of individual settings and capabilities, taking into account users' needs.
Principle 3: Simple and Convenient Use	Design should be characterized by simplicity and intuitiveness regardless of users' experience, education, language proficiency, and age.
Principle 4: Information Perception Regardless of Users' Sensory Abilities	Design facilitates effective delivery of all necessary information to the user, regardless of external conditions or the user's perception capabilities.
Principle 5: Tolerance for Errors	Design minimizes the possibility of risks and harmful consequences of accidental or unintentional actions by users.
Principle 6: Low Physical Effort	Design promotes efficient and convenient use with minimal levels of fatigue. It is designed for minimal physical effort that users must exert.
Principle 7: Availability of Sufficient Size and Space for Approach, Entry, and Various Manipulations	Design provides adequate size and space for access and use, taking into account the user's body size, mobility, and more

Source: compiled by authors on materials [7]

People with disabilities face numerous challenges in the tourism sector. The inaccessibility of infrastructure, including the lack of ramps and lifts, complicates movement for individuals with mobility limitations. Limited or nonexistent information about the accessibility of tourist attractions and the high cost of specialized services are also significant issues in modern society. In addition, incompetent staff and the absence of adapted transportation further complicate the travel process for people with disabilities. Social unawareness and the lack of specialized entertainment also hinder their tourism experience. Addressing these problems requires a comprehensive approach, including the creation of accessible infrastructure, improvement of staff training, development of accessible information, and raising social awareness.

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought significant changes to the tourism industry, and inclusive tourism is no exception. During the COVID-19 pandemic, new challenges and opportunities have emerged for inclusive tourism. Regarding difficulties, many infrastructure facilities that were already inaccessible to people with disabilities became even less accessible due to the introduction of additional restrictions and sanitary measures. The cancellation of events and changes in public transport operations have also complicated travel for individuals with disabilities.

However, the pandemic has also opened up new opportunities for inclusive tourism. The increasing popularity of remote entertainment and cultural events has opened up opportunities to provide access to such events for people who previously may have felt restricted in their participation due to physical limitations or other reasons. Additionally, during the

quarantine period, more attention was given to digital technologies and virtual events, which became a new tool for inclusive tourism, allowing people with disabilities to experience tourism in an online environment. In any case, the development of inclusive tourism during the COVID-19 pandemic requires attention to the safety and health of all tourists, including those with special needs, emphasizing the importance of adapting infrastructure and services to accommodate new realities in the tourism industry.

Inclusive tourism plays a significant role in improving the quality of life for people with disabilities. By providing accessible infrastructure and services, it enhances the mobility and independence of this group of individuals. Promoting social integration, inclusive tourism breaks down social barriers and fosters a diverse and open community. Participation in cultural and recreational activities enriches cultural experiences and enhances self-esteem and independence. The development of inclusive tourism also contributes to economic participation by creating new job opportunities and increasing the financial independence of this population group. Overall, inclusive tourism promotes the creation of a more integrated and equitable society, where every individual has the opportunity to enjoy life to the fullest.

Ukraine, at the initial stage of its development in the field of inclusive tourist rehabilitation for people with disabilities, already plays an important role in the context of a comprehensive approach to integrating the target audience into the social environment, which is significant in the European context. Despite initial limitations, people with disabilities show active

interest in accessing modern tourist-rehabilitation services. Currently, although some public organizations provide similar tourist-rehabilitation services, this is done inconsistently and without proper consideration of individual rehabilitation needs. The issue of rehabilitation becomes acute not only for people with disabilities but also for those who have become participants or suffered as a result of military events in Ukraine. In the next stage of development, research and the development of travel routes with the main requirement - accessibility of such places for people with various limitations are planned. In addition

to tourist rehabilitation, the implementation of vocational and employment services is envisaged, which will open up new opportunities and self-realization for people with disabilities. Such an integrated approach sets the task for Ukraine of systematic development of inclusive tourism and full rehabilitation, taking into account the needs of different population groups [11].

Key factors contributing to the adaptation of people with disabilities when using inclusive tourism include: livelihood, recreation and rehabilitation, socialization, and communication. Let's consider each factor in fig. 1.

Figure 1. Factors Facilitating Adaptation of Persons with Disabilities in Inclusive Tourism

Source: compiled by authors on materials [6]

The situation with armed conflict in Ukraine negatively affects various aspects of society, including tourism and inclusive tourism in particular. Military conflicts and the unstable situation overall create numerous difficulties and limitations for all population groups, including people with disabilities. Infrastructure that may be essential for inclusive tourism can be damaged or inaccessible during war. The destruction and restricted access to tourism sites, including hotels, museums, and other attractions, undoubtedly complicate travel for people with disabilities. Additionally, the wartime situation may lead to evacuations and population displacements, further complicating not only travel itself but also the provision of specialized services for people with disabilities, who may require additional assistance and support. It is important to note that in conditions of armed conflict, the priority is the safety of all citizens, and the development of tourism, including inclusive tourism, may be postponed due to more pressing tasks in crisis conditions.

The general instability and danger associated with military conflict complicate any attempts at tourism development, including inclusive tourism. In such circumstances, it is important to focus on restoring peace and stability before actively developing the tourism sector in an inclusive context.

Unfortunately, after armed conflict in Ukraine, especially in regions directly affected by the conflict, infrastructure and tourism sector recovery and development become challenging. The popularity of inclusive tourism may emerge in the context of post-conflict reconstruction and rehabilitation efforts. Efforts to restore infrastructure may include the

creation or adaptation of facilities to ensure accessibility for all tourists, including those with special needs. This may involve constructing accessible hotels, restaurants, museums, and providing other services catering to the needs of people with disabilities. The role of civil society and non-profit organizations in the restoration and support of inclusive tourism is also crucial. Initiatives to support and develop tourism that addresses the needs of various population groups can contribute to attracting tourists and promoting economic recovery in affected regions.

The overall success of inclusive tourism after wartime in Ukraine will be determined not only by the level of infrastructure restoration but also by tourists' interest in visiting and supporting these regions.

Investments in tourism for people with disabilities can have significant social and economic impacts on society. Investing in adapting tourism infrastructure for people with disabilities will create more accessible hotels, restaurants, transportation, and other tourist attractions. Investment in staff training and professional programs will improve the quality of service for tourists with disabilities, ensuring a more comfortable and enjoyable experience for them. Investments in research and development of new technologies and innovative solutions for inclusive tourism can create new services and opportunities for this category of tourists. Investment in marketing and promotion of inclusive tourism will help draw attention to this sector and increase its popularity among tourists with disabilities. Investment in programs and initiatives aimed at supporting social integration for people with disabilities through tourism can help

reduce social distance and increase their participation in society.

Overall, investments in tourism for people with disabilities will contribute to creating a more inclusive, fair, and equal society, as well as promoting the development of the tourism industry as a whole. Diversification of tourism for people with disabilities in social integration is an important aspect of creating an inclusive environment that considers the needs and desires of this category of tourists.

Providing a diverse range of tourism services and offerings will allow people with disabilities to choose options that best suit their needs and preferences. This may include access to various types of recreational activities, cultural events, tours, and other forms of entertainment. Creating adapted routes and tours that take into account the needs of people with different types of disabilities (such as routes for people with visual impairments, routes for visiting neglected architectural sites for people with mobility impairments, etc.) is essential.

Investing in the construction and support of specialized infrastructure facilities, such as adapted hotels, beaches, parks, attractions, and other tourist sites, that meet the needs of this audience is crucial. Developing education and training programs for tour operators, hotels, and other service providers to increase their awareness and ability to serve customers with disabilities is important.

Collaborating with civil society organizations and community representatives can help identify the needs and preferences of the target audience and develop programs accordingly. In general, diversifying tourism for people with disabilities contributes to creating a more inclusive and accessible tourism environment, allowing this category of people to actively participate in social life and cultural exchange.

Marine tourism for people with disabilities is an important direction that promotes their social integration and provides access to a variety of recreational opportunities. This form of tourism allows people with various disabilities to enjoy the beauty of the sea, sun, and beaches, as well as participate in various maritime adventures and excursions.

Some cruise companies and tour operators offer adapted cruises and sea trips for people with disabilities, using special transport with lifts, wide doors, and other conveniences. Many hotels and port cities strive to ensure accessibility for people with various types of disabilities by installing ramps, special lifts, and other facilities. In addition, some cruise lines offer adapted excursions and entertainment on board for people with disabilities, allowing them to enjoy maritime adventures and explore new places alongside other tourists.

Marine tourism can also provide opportunities for social interaction and communication for people with disabilities, allowing them to connect with other passengers and engage in pleasant conversations in a welcoming atmosphere. Overall, marine tourism for people with disabilities is an important factor in their social integration, expanding their opportunities for leisure, development, and communication.

In the context of tourism for people with disabilities, united territorial communities (UTCs) play an important role in promoting their social integration and ensuring access to tourism opportunities.

United territorial communities can initiate projects for the development of tourism infrastructure that takes into account the needs of people with various types of disabilities. This includes the construction of accessible hotels, ramps, adapted transportation, and other facilities. United territorial communities can contribute to the organization of tourist events and excursions that cater to the needs and interests of people with disabilities. These may include special tourist routes, excursions with specialized equipment, and other events.

United territorial communities can organize training for the staff of hotels, restaurants, tourist agencies, and other businesses to enable them to provide quality service to people with disabilities. They can also promote tourism services and attractions for people with disabilities to attract more attention to the target audience and increase their participation in tourism.

United territorial communities can establish partnerships with civil society organizations working in the field of supporting people with disabilities to jointly develop and implement projects for inclusive tourism. Overall, united territorial communities have the potential to become significant catalysts for creating an accessible and inclusive tourism environment that promotes the social integration of people with disabilities.

Conclusion

Inclusive tourism for people with disabilities is an advanced direction in modern tourism aimed at involving everyone in tourist visits, regardless of their physical abilities and characteristics of their physical and psychological condition. This form of tourism is considered an effective tool for active rehabilitation as it includes various types of recovery and social services, such as medical, psychological, psycho-pedagogical, professional, labor, physical, social, and others. Inclusive tourism aims to provide full and accessible recreation for all, promoting physical and emotional recovery, as well as the inclusion of people with disabilities in society through new opportunities and experiences. Tourism for people with disabilities plays a key role in their social integration by facilitating travel and visiting tourist sites through the creation of accessible infrastructure. Such tourism promotes active interaction between different groups of people, fostering social integration and understanding. Additionally, it broadens cultural experiences, helping to understand and appreciate diversity. Active participation in inclusive tourism positively impacts the self-esteem and independence of people with disabilities. This approach also opens up new economic opportunities and contributes to the development of specialized services. In summary, tourism for this population group plays an important role in building an inclusive and equitable society.

Such inclusive tourism is not only a means of travel but also a powerful tool for social transformation. Its impact extends far beyond the boundaries of the tourist experience, as it contributes to the creation of a more open, equal, and diverse society. Providing accessible infrastructure and services sets new standards, making tourism accessible to all.

This approach also actively promotes cultural interaction and understanding among different segments of the population, fostering a more tolerant society. The positive impact on the self-esteem and independence of persons with disabilities underscores the importance of their active participation in social and cultural events. Additionally, inclusive tourism serves as a catalyst for economic development by creating jobs and expanding entrepreneurial activities in this field.

In summary, inclusive tourism opens up new horizons for social integration, mutual understanding, and economic development. Its role in shaping a modern society that values and embraces diversity is paramount, as it provides the means to promote active and fulfilling lives for all its participants.

Tourism holds significant importance for the social integration of people with disabilities. This sector not only provides opportunities for leisure and recreation but also facilitates the active involvement of this population group in societal life. Through access to tourist attractions, infrastructure, and services, people with disabilities have the opportunity to showcase their abilities and skills, expand their social networks, embrace new cultural interpretations, and enrich their life experiences. Moreover, the development of inclusive tourism contributes to raising society's

awareness of the needs and rights of people with disabilities, thus fostering the creation of a more equitable and inclusive society for all its members. Therefore, it is important to continue developing projects and initiatives aimed at creating an accessible and inclusive tourism environment that supports the social integration of people with disabilities.

Prospects for further research lie in expanding understanding of the role of tourism in the social integration of people with disabilities. Research on the accessibility of tourist attractions and leisure facilities for people with various types of disabilities will help identify gaps in accessibility and develop strategies to overcome them. Analyzing the impact of participation in tourism programs and events on the quality of life of people with disabilities, including their social integration, self-esteem, and sense of independence. Creating new models and approaches to the development of inclusive tourism that take into account the needs and desires of people with disabilities, with the aim of creating a more accessible and inclusive environment. Conducting research in collaboration with NGOs, tourism companies, and government agencies to develop and implement programs and policies aimed at supporting inclusive tourism. Analyzing the cultural and social aspects of tourism on the social integration of people with disabilities, including identifying possible barriers and incentives for their participation in tourism programs. Research in these areas will not only deepen our understanding of the role of tourism in social integration but also contribute to the development and implementation of more effective programs and initiatives in the field of inclusive tourism.

Abstract

Inclusive tourism is a tourism direction aimed at creating accessible and inclusive conditions for travel for everyone, including people with disabilities or other special needs. The primary goal of inclusive tourism is to ensure equal opportunities for all tourists, regardless of their physical or cognitive abilities.

This approach involves the creation and support of accessible tourist infrastructure, as well as the development of programs and services that take into account the diverse needs of tourists. Inclusive tourism may include accessible hotels, transportation, attractions, tours, and other tourist services. This approach not only promotes the inclusion of individuals with disabilities in tourism events but also recognizes and values the diversity of needs among different populations. Inclusive tourism contributes to creating a more accessible and equitable environment for all tourists.

The article examines key aspects related to inclusive tourism and its impact on the social integration of individuals with disabilities in Ukraine for the period 2017-2021. The article sheds light on the increasing number of people with disabilities and defines the concept of inclusive tourism, its development, and its goal of facilitating the inclusion of the target audience into society. The interconnection between inclusive tourism and social integration is investigated, emphasizing the importance of the participation of individuals with disabilities in tourist events and programs. Additionally, the article analyzes the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on inclusive tourism and explores possibilities for overcoming difficulties arising from travel restrictions. Successful initiatives and projects in inclusive tourism in Ukraine are cited, contributing to the active involvement of people with disabilities in recreational activities. Notably, examples include the creation of accessible tourist routes.

The article separately highlights the system of principles of universal design, emphasizing "accessible and convenient for all," as a tool for creating inclusive and friendly environments for people with various types of limitations. Furthermore, the article examines factors contributing to the adaptation of tourist infrastructure to include individuals with disabilities in inclusive tourism.

In conclusion, the article underscores the importance of inclusive tourism as a tool for social integration and addresses current issues related to the development of this field. It takes into account not only the demand for such services but also the challenges arising from external factors, such as the pandemic. The comprehensive overview emphasizes the need for continuous efforts and considerations in promoting inclusive tourism in Ukraine.

Список літератури:

1. Інклюзивний туризм. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/300240771.pdf#page=17>.
2. Аналіз розвитку інклюзивного туризму закордоном. DOI: 10.26565/2310H9513H2020H11H14.
3. Особливості інклюзивного туризму. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: https://tourlib.net/statti_ukr/vojtovska.htm.
4. Формування доступного середовища інклюзивного туризму. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://er.chdtu.edu.ua/bitstream/ChSTU/3191/1/113--3~1.PDF>.
5. Розвиток інклюзивного туризму. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: https://eprints.kname.edu.ua/58508/1/%D0%9C%D0%9A%D0%A6_2021_%D0%BF%D0%BE%D1%81%D0%BB_26.pdf#page=38.
6. Логунова Н.А. Управління інноваційним розвитком круїзного бізнесу. Економіка розвитку. 2013. № 2 (66). Стор. 95-99.
7. Принципи універсального дизайну. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://ud.org.ua/publikatsiji/11-printsipi-universalnogo-dizajnu>.
8. Accessible Tourism Solutions to Make Destinations and Traveler Experiences More Inclusive. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://www.trainingaid.org/ideas-and-insights/accessible-tourism-solutions-businesses-and-destinations>.
9. UNWTO. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <http://www.unwto.org>.
10. Соціальний захист населення України у 2020 році. Державна служба статистики України. Київ, 2021. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://ukrstat.gov.ua/druk/publicat/kat_u/2021/zb/07/zb_szn_2020.pdf.
11. Інклюзивний туризм для осіб з інвалідністю. Офіційний вебпортал Фонду соціального захисту людей з інвалідністю. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://www.ispf.gov.ua/news/inklyuzivnyy-turizm-dlya-osib-z-invalidnistyu>.
12. Добрянська Н.А. Управління інвестиційним процесом Одеської області / Н.А. Добрянська, А.А. Капелюшна // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2019. – № 4 (44). – С. 32-39 – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2019/No4/32.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3757391.
13. Добрянська Н.А. Еволюція диверсифікації виробництва, мотиви та її цілі [Електронний ресурс] / Н.А. Добрянська, А.А. Нікіфорчук // Ефективна економіка. – 2013. – №9. – Режим доступу до журналу: <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua>.
14. Добрянська Н.А. Сучасний стан та перспективи розвитку морського круїзного туризму в Одеській області / Н.А. Добрянська, А.С. Володівщук, Р.А. Добрянський // Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету. – 2019. – № 4 (10). – С. 50-56. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejoru/2019/No4/50.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6483207.
15. Dobrianska N., Nikoliuk O., Lebedieva V. Organizational and economic measures of tourism development on the example of the Avangard United Territorial Community of Odessa region // Food Industry Economics. 2019. Vol.11, Issue 3. P. 88-96.

References:

1. Inclusive tourism. Retrieved from: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/300240771.pdf#page=17> [in Ukrainian].
2. Analysis of the development of inclusive tourism abroad. DOI: 10.26565/2310H9513H2020H11H14 [in Ukrainian].
3. Features of inclusive tourism. Retrieved from: https://tourlib.net/statti_ukr/vojtovska.htm [in Ukrainian].
4. Formation of an accessible middle ground for inclusive tourism. Retrieved from: <https://er.chdtu.edu.ua/bitstream/ChSTU/3191/1/113--3~1.PDF> [in Ukrainian].
5. Development of inclusive tourism. Retrieved from: https://eprints.kname.edu.ua/58508/1/%D0%9C%D0%9A%D0%A6_2021_%D0%BF%D0%BE%D1%81%D0%BB_26.pdf#page=38 [in Ukrainian].
6. Logunova, N.A. (2013). Management of innovative development of cruise business. Economic development, No. 2 (66). Pp. 95-99 [in Ukrainian].
7. Principles of universal design. Retrieved from: <https://ud.org.ua/publikatsiji/11-printsipi-universalnogo-dizajnu> [in Ukrainian].

8. Accessible Tourism Solutions to Make Destinations and Traveler Experiences More Inclusive. Retrieved from: <https://www.trainingaid.org/ideas-and-insights/accessible-tourism-solutions-businesses-and-destinations> [in English].
9. UNWTO. Retrieved from: <http://www.unwto.org> [in English].
10. Social protection of the population of Ukraine in 2020. State Statistics Service of Ukraine. (2021). Kiev. Retrieved from: http://ukrstat.gov.ua/druk/publicat/kat_u/2021/zb/07/zb_szn_2020.pdf [in Ukrainian].
11. Inclusive tourism for people with disabilities. Official web portal of the Foundation for Social Protection of People with Disabilities. Retrieved from: <https://www.ispf.gov.ua/news/inklyuzivniy-turizm-dlya-osib-z-invalidnistyu> [in Ukrainian].
12. Dobrianska, N.A., & Kapeliushna, A.A. (2019). Management of the investment process of the Odessa region. Economics: time realities. Scientific journal, № 4 (44), P. 32-39. Retrieved from: <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2019/No4/32.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3757391 [in Ukrainian].
13. Dobrianska, N.A., & Nikiforchuk, A.A. (2013). Evolution of production diversification, motives, and its goals. Efficient economy, No.9. Retrieved from: <http://www.economy.nayka.com.ua> [in Ukrainian].
14. Dobrianskaya, N.A., Volodivschuk, A.S. & Dobrianskyi, R.A. (2019). The current state and development prospects of sea cruise tourism in the Odessa region. Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university, № 4 (10). Pp. 50-56. Retrieved from: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2019/No4/50.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6483207 [in Ukrainian].
15. Dobrianska, N., Nikoliuk, O., Lebedieva, V. (2019). Organizational and economic measures of tourism development on the example of the Avangard United Territorial Community of Odessa region. Food Industry Economics, Vol.11, Issue 3. P. 88-96 [in English].

Посилання на статтю:

Dobrianska N.A. The Role of Tourism for People with Disabilities in Social Integration / N.A. Dobrianska, D.S. Kurchenko, O.O. Nesterchuk // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2024. – № 3 (73). – С. 44-52. – Режим доступу: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2024/No3/44.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.03.2024.5. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12692145.

Reference a Journal Article:

Dobrianska N.A. The Role of Tourism for People with Disabilities in Social Integration / N.A. Dobrianska, D.S. Kurchenko, O.O. Nesterchuk // Economics: time realities. Scientific journal. – 2024. – № 3 (73). – P. 44-52. – Retrieved from: <https://economics.net.ua/files/archive/2024/No3/44.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.03.2024.5. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12692145.

